

MODERN TEACHING TECHNIQUES IN EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

Modern Teaching Techniques have been spread all over the world, which is useful and easy for teachers. Modern Teaching Techniques educate children well and make them understand clearly. In this era, there is an increased usage of the internet in educational applications; this could mean that students and teachers will increasingly make use of technology within open and flexible learning systems. Technology plays an important role in enhancing and developing our learning system. Intended outcomes as well as unintended results of using Modern Teaching Techniques for teacher professional development need to be explored. Certain skills and capabilities of using different Modern Teaching Technologies are necessary for students as well as teachers. Therefore it is necessary to prepare them for the age of Modern Teaching Technology.

key words: *modern Teaching Techniques, Objectives, Classification of Teaching Techniques, Teaching Techniques, Medias, Benefits, Preparation for Modern Age*

Introduction

Education is a process by which the personality of a child is developed. Thus the education of tomorrow should be able to play its role more effectively by making the individual creative, innovative and effective. One teacher would be unable to cater to the various individual differences of all the students. Modern Teaching Technique is important and most preferred in the technological age. Nowadays, as classes are modified and equipped with Modern teaching aids such as Speakers, Online Streaming Videos, Interactive Whiteboards, Visualizer,

Response System, CD's, Projectors, Educational Software etc, it acts as a tool for the teachers to explain the concepts in a more effective and lucid manner. Teachers can teach the students with more depth and efficiency and also clear all their doubts with Modern Teaching Techniques. Teachers must use various types of Modern Teaching Techniques to connect with the students. This paper deals with the Modern Teaching Techniques that are used in Education. These techniques help to attain the following objectives.

Objectives

Present the material in more interesting and attractive way, Guide and help the students in enriching the qualitative material, Make best use of time and coach the students, Provide individualized instruction, Direct the students toward cooperative as well as collaborative learning activities, Prepare the learning material for students, rather teaching in conventional situations, Diagnose the learning of students and help them to overcome their study problems

1. Techniques associated with Teaching Method

Brain Storming, Micro Teaching Technique, Programmed Learning, Inquiry-Based Learning, Mind Map, Cooperative Learning, Dramatization

2. Media involved in Modern Teaching Techniques

Audio Aids, Visual Aids, Audio-Visual Aids, Interactive Electronic White Board
Modern Teaching Techniques Among these classifications, some of the Modern Teaching Techniques with the help of advanced technology are frequently adopted in classrooms. We can see them in a detailed manner.

Brain Storming:

It is a group creativity technique that was designed to generate a large number of ideas for the solution of a problem. Problem solving is a process to choose and use the effective and beneficial tool and behaviors among the different potentialities to reach the target. It contains scientific method, critical thinking, taking decision, examining and reflective thinking. This method is used in the process of solving a problem to generalize or to make synthesis. It provides students to face the problems boldly

and to deal with it in a scientific approach. It helps students to adopt the view of benefit from others ideas and to help each other.

Micro Teaching Technique:

It is essential to practice the teaching skills in order to become better teachers. A teaching skill is a set of teaching behaviors of the teacher which is especially effective in bringing about desired changes in pupils' behavior. Allen and Ryan in 1966 identified 20 teaching skills at Stanford University. This list has now increased to 37 teaching skills. These skills can be assessed by means of an observation scales. It is not possible to train all the pupil teachers in all these skills in any training program because of the constraints of time and funds. Therefore a set of teaching skills which cuts across the subject areas has been identified. They have been found to be very useful for every teacher. The set of these skills are Skill of Probing Questions, Skill of Explaining, Skill of Illustrating with Examples, Skill of Reinforcement, Skill of Stimulus Variation, Skill of Classroom Management and Skill of using Blackboard.

Programmed Learning:

Programmed learning (or programmed instruction) is a research-based system which helps learners work successfully. The learning material may be a textbook or teaching machine or computer. The medium presents the material in a logical and tested sequence. The text is in small steps or larger chunks. After each step, learners are given a question to test their comprehension. Then immediately the correct answer is shown. This means the learner at all stages makes responses, and is given immediate knowledge of results.

Inquiry-Based Learning:

Inquiry-based learning starts by posing questions, problems or scenarios—rather than simply presenting established facts or portraying a smooth path to knowledge. The process is often assisted by a facilitator. Inquirers will identify and research issues and questions to develop their knowledge or solutions. The inquiry-based

instruction is principally very closely related to the development and practice of thinking skills.

Mind Map:

It is one of the Innovative teaching techniques. It was developed by Tony Buzan in 1960. Mind Maps are used as learning and teaching technique. Mind Map visually illustrates the relationship between concepts and ideas. Often represented in circles or boxes, concepts are linked by words and phrases that explain the connection between the ideas, helping the students, organize and structure their thoughts to further understand information and discover new relationships. Recollect information for long time. Mind map help for better learning and effective achievement.

Cooperative Learning:

It is a successful teaching technique in which small teams, each with students of different levels of ability, use variety of learning activities to improve their understanding of a subject. Each member of a team is responsible not only for learning what is taught but also for helping team mates learning, thus creating the atmosphere of achievement. Students work through the assignment until all the members successfully understand and complete it. Cooperative efforts result in participants striving for mutual benefit for all the group members .

Dramatization:

One of the Modern teaching techniques teaches students how to behave in a situation by living it. Physical environment/costumes/accessories are important and they effect the concentration of the students. Students use their own imagination thus improving their creativeness. It provides direct involvement in learning on the part of all students, improves their language usage, communicating/speaking and listening skills and allows for the exploration of solutions. The various types of Dramatization are Informal drama, Role playing, Formal drama, Puppets, Pantomime and Finger game.

Media involved in Modern Teaching Techniques

Audio Aids:

In the recent past these hearing aids like cassettes and recorders were in used in the process of learning of English language. Such teaching aids were effective in improving the phonetics, pronunciation and spoken English of the students.

Visual Aids:

Apart from the traditional visual aids like charts, pictures and models that are still in use in the classrooms, there are other modern visual aids which were in use in the recent years.

These aids include the picture slides, motion pictures and the like. The modern times, the development in technology e-book readers which are portable electronic devices are mainly used for reading digital books.

Audio-Visual Aids:

These are being widely adopted and used in many of the educational institutions, which have a separate audio-visual room or lab. By the growth of technology children are showing much interest in computer-based learning like the Power point presentations. It develops team work among the students as they are required to work in teams for such project based learning. In such a Project based learning teacher acts as a facilitator to the taught and this involves the active participation of the student.

Interactive Electronic White Board:

This is a very recent development wherein the whole board acts like a touch screen with students being able to do various manipulations directly on the board itself. Basically the white electronic board is connected to a digital projector which projects the material on the computer onto the board. Then without the need of touching the computer, the students can do mathematical calculations, scrabble solving etc by the use of a stylus provided.

Conclusion

Using Modern Teaching Technologies, learners are now able to participate in the activities of the learning communities throughout the world. They may learn collaboratively, share information, exchange their learning experiences and work

through cooperative activities in virtual learning communities. Modern Teaching Technologies facilitate teaching and learning process in more productive fashion. In a nutshell, Modern Teaching Technologies are restructuring the teaching learning process to meet the International standards.

USED LITERATURE

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